

Ritual Continuity and Symbolic Representation: A Comparative Cultural Study of Sangam Literature and Megalithic Traditions of the Nilgiri Hills

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Abstract

This research paper, "Rituals and Symbolism in Sangam and Megalithic Traditions of the Nilgiris," explores the interrelationship between Sangam age rituals and symbolism and those that took place in the southern part of Tamil Nadu, as well as their similarities with the megalithic traditions of the Nilgiris. Sangam literature, such as Agananuru and Purananuru, mentions rituals and symbolism that have been followed since the megalithic period. Today, in Nilgiris, the megalithic traditions, symbolism, and rituals from the Sangam period are still practiced and followed by indigenous tribal communities, including the Toda, Kota, Kurumba, Irulas, Paniya, Kattunayaka, and Baduga. This paper explores how rituals and symbolism in the Sangam age are connected to the Nilgiris' megalithic period and how cultural continuity is practiced by the tribes in the Nilgiris.

Keywords: Megalithic Culture, Ritual, Symbolism, Literature

Introduction

The Sangam age, dating from the 3rd century BCE to the 3rd century CE in the southern part of Tamil Nadu, provides ample literary evidence of how ritual and symbolism were used by the Tamil people. The Megalithic Culture in Tamil Nadu, including the Iron Age, is dated from 1000 BCE to 300 CE. The Nilgiris, located in the northwestern part of Tamil Nadu, boasts a rich historical background, and megalithic culture is widely present in the Nilgiris District. Megalithic monuments such as dolmens, cairn circles, and rock art sites are found in the Nilgiris, and all tribal groups in the Nilgiris have followed the megalithic culture. Many questions arise regarding the prehistoric period of megalithic culture, with no records or evidence to prove its continuation into modern times. The answer to this question is not simple, but we do have one: megalithic monuments have become shrines for local deities and ancestral worship practices. Some rock art images have been linked to present-day practices, indicating that the tribal community has been living

in the Nilgiris for centuries and worshipping ancestral gods. In the Sangam age, there is a mention of ancestral worship, and most importantly, Hero Stones (Nadukal) that have been worshipped by the tribes in the Nilgiris. There is evidence of ancestral worship in Sangam literature. Additionally, some dolmens with hero stones indicate the practice of demigod worship. Sangam literature is rich in descriptions of the landscape, lifestyle, heroism, kingship, and death rituals. The coexistence of Sangam references to megalithic practices in the Nilgiris and the continued use of symbols and rituals by the indigenous groups of the Nilgiris in the present day offers a unique anthropological bridge between the past and present. Therefore, this study examines the interconnection of shared rituals, symbolic frameworks, burial traditions, hero-memorialization, fertility rituals, pastoral rituals, and the sacred landscape from the Sangam period to the megalithic period and its continuity in the present day in the Nilgiris District.

Historical Background

The Sangam literature is one of the oldest literary sources found in the world. If we delve into the literary sources, there are two prominent collections: the Ettuttogai (Eight Anthologies) and the Pattuppattu (Ten Idylls), along with the grammar treatise Tolkāppiyam and the later Five Great Epics: Silappatikaram, Manimekalai, Civaka Cintamani, Valayapathi, and Kundalakesi. These Sangam literary sources, including the five great epics, provide significant insights and scenarios regarding megalithic burial practices, megalithic culture, ancestor worship, and, most prominently, the practice of erecting hero stones (Nadukal).

The literature acts as a bridge between the archaeological evidence of the Iron Age megalithic period and the social life of the Sangam era. Society during this era was organized around five eco-cultural landscapes (Tinai): Kurinji, Mullai, Marutham, Neithal, and Palai. For comparative study, Kurinji is denoted as a Hill station. The Nilgiri megalithic period is one of the prominent sites in Tamil Nadu and also is significant for consisting of six indigenous tribal communities in Nilgiri: Todas, Kotas, Irulas, Kurumbas, Paniyas, and Kattunayakas. Additionally, there are the Badagas, who are not a primitive tribal community but are indigenous people living in the Nilgiris with a larger population. These tribal communities are still practicing the megalithic traditions mentioned in the Sangam literature today.

Archaeological, anthropological, and ethnographic studies have shown that these indigenous groups have been following megalithic traditions for centuries. The rituals and ceremonial practices, especially the death rituals and the symbolism used by the tribal communities, highlight the living tradition and achievements of ancient ritual culture and provide a foundation for comparative study and analysis between the megalithic period in the Nilgiris and the Sangam era.

Common Mortuary Beliefs and Burial Rituals

In Sangam literature, there is explicit content describing burial rituals, ceremonial rituals, and secondary burials, documented in Agananuru and Purananuru. These texts refer to urn burials, cairn circles, and memorial stones, indicating that death was considered a part of life. These rituals had a connection with nature, which explains the ceremonial practices and the symbolism associated with natural elements like the sun, moon, stars, flowers, and animals. These elements were linked to the lifestyle in ancient times and were practiced by indigenous tribal communities in the Nilgiris.

These mortuary beliefs and burial rituals were practiced during the Sangam period and continued by indigenous tribal groups, not only in the Nilgiris but also among Southeast Asian indigenous tribes. These practices correspond directly to the megalithic excavations done in the Nilgiris, where dolmens, urn burials, and menhirs were unearthed. Grave goods, ornaments, and pottery were found placed with the deceased, reflecting ancestral worship and the belief in an afterlife where the soul

would enjoy its existence. The Toda, Kota, and Kurumba communities have been following and continuing these rituals and ceremonial practices by placing remembrance stones and meaningful objects with the deceased. This demonstrates the long-term preservation of megalithic funeral ceremonies.

Hero Worship and Memorial Stones

One of the most prominent and significant features of the Sangam literary tradition, alongside the monumental practices in the Nilgiris, is the practice of Hero worship. If a well-known figure or a person who lost his life during a battle or any sporting event, they will be honored by their burial. For their remembrance, they are often constructed or kept as a memorial stone, known as Herostones (Nadukal). This reverence symbolizes bravery and the most significant aspect is to transform the ordinary individual into a spiritual guardian. For the entire community, this individual will be celebrated and regarded as a divine figure, and in this context, future generations will respect and practice ancestor worship.

Excavations have been conducted in the Nilgiris, and it has been proven that this archaeological site is the ancestral burial ground. In Baduga communities, the Hethai Habba and Kota memorial stones traditions have continued this legacy, demonstrating the uncountable rituals and ceremonial practices from the Iron Age to the present day.

Pastoral Symbolism and the Ritual Economy

Pastoral Life, cattle wealth, and buffaloes were symbolic representations of both the Sangam and Mulla landscape. During the Sangam period, cattle were viewed as the people's companionship, and they celebrated festivals for them. This also served as economic security for the people, as they regarded cattle as their asset. This can be seen in the literature from the Sangam period.

The two prominent tribal groups, Todas and Baduga, have been operating in Nilgiris. The Todas are primarily engaged in cattle farming, while the Baduga utilize cows for milk production and economic activities. The Buffaloes, on the other hand, are primarily used as animal companions, rather than as a distinct animal. They regard the buffalo as their companions, and more than that, they consider it as a guardian soul who has guided the tribal community for centuries.

In the Sangam literature, it is mentioned that they celebrate festivals for the cattle, similar practices were observed by Toda. They are known as "Modhweth", which is commonly referred to as the Buffaloes Festivals. They also celebrate the festival annually. The term "Kedu" is often referred to as the funeral rituals.

The buffaloes, which are used as a ritual entity, and the milk produced from them, are used in their lifestyle from birth, marriage, death, and seasonal ceremonies. Similarly, festivals like Indra Vilzha, which celebrates the cattle, also involve the celebration of milk. The Toda people, on the other hand, utilize milk and its products as a commodity, and as a barter system, they purchase pottery from the Kota tribes. They use the pottery for rituals and ceremonial practices.

Ancestral Memory and Collective Identity

Both the Sangam Age and the Megalithic culture share a similarity when it comes to ancestor memory. Ancestor worship is a source of identity and cultural roots. Sangam poems describe heroic worship and how people practiced venerating a leader, who then became a spiritual guide for the people, a tradition passed down for centuries. A similar concept has been followed by tribal groups in the Nilgiris.

Both cultures rely on the concept of rebirth and an afterlife. They also offer sacrifices and perform rituals that connect with nature. If we examine the Toda death ceremonies, we can see this.

They involve flowing water, which runs continuously, symbolizing their belief that after death, they will flow like water and continue into the afterlife. Mostly, Sangam literature mentions death rituals practiced on riverbanks, indicating that water is an essential source for these rituals.

Moreover, an important aspect is that, similar to Sangam literature, which describes heroes who died for their people and land in poems, clearly detailing their bravery and heroism, the oral traditions and folklore stories of tribal communities also feature songs that represent ancestors who fought for their land, people, and culture. This creates an unbroken chain of ancestor veneration. This belief is not just about ceremonial practices; it represents a cultural continuity from the past to the present, practiced by the tribal groups of the Nilgiris.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Sangam period and the Megalithic culture in Nilgiri share similarities in ritual continuity and symbolic representation. The megalithic monuments in Nilgiri, the evidence of burial sites, and the methods of burial show a pattern that has been followed by present-day tribal groups in the Nilgiris, including their ritual practices. The death ceremonies noted in the Sangam period are also observed by these tribal groups. Both cultures feature memorial stones, or hero stones, which represent individuals who fought for their people, culture, and land. These figures become spiritual guides and are revered. This fascinating practice is followed not only in Tamil Nadu but also across the southeastern part of Asia.

Another notable aspect is the symbolic representation. Symbols are deeply rooted, culturally connecting and civilizing us. Most importantly, the Nilgiri region is mentioned as a Kurinji tinai, describing its flora and fauna, which matches present-day observations. Thus, it is not fiction but a documented work by authors from the Sangam age. This documented record shows the antiquity of the civilization; megalithic monuments were constructed before the prehistoric period. These monuments are still in use today and are not considered mere historical artifacts but shrines where people perform rituals, prayers, and ceremonial acts. This practice is mentioned in Sangam literature and continues in modern times. Therefore, the people of the Nilgiri have a long-standing tradition of following their customs. Not only that, they have been transferring these customs and traditions to the next generation, even though they face many challenges due to modernization.

They still strive to preserve their culture and teach future generations not to forget their traditions, their roots, and their origins. They learn about their ancestors, why they worship them, how all this is connected to nature, and how nature is central to all these customs and traditions. These monuments are built in different shapes, and each has a story. The pottery used for rituals is an element of the earth and ultimately represents that the people belong to nature. When people die, they are believed to have an afterlife, signifying that still a soul is roaming in nature. The legacy continues because these leaders were not just people who died; they were guardians who became protectors for the community.

And thus the stone continues to speak its legacy, and the history is written in the books; however, the roots are never lost.

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